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Efficacy of insect pollinators on seed production of two onion (*Allium cepa*) varieties, Gezira State, Sudan

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Abstract

Pollination is the process by which pollen is transferred to the female reproductive organs of a plant, thereby enabling fertilization to take place. Hence, pollination is a keystone process in both human-managed and natural terrestrial ecosystems. Over 80% of the crops grown in Europe are dependent on insect pollination. Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is ranked second only to tomatoes in terms of total annual world production. The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of insect pollinators on seed production of two onion (*A. cepa*) varieties (Baftaim and Balady). Also, to identify the insect pollinators diversity associated with the onion crop in the location. The study was carried out at Wad Medani at the Experimental Farm of the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences (Open pollination), University of Gezira. Data on seed production and assessing the seed yield of onion in tested varieties under insect pollinators. Also, identify the insect pollinator diversity associated with the onion crop in the location. An experiment was laid out on a Complete Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with four different treatments and three replications at the site in the cropping season of 2019-2020. The result revealed that there were significant differences among treatments. Baftaim and Balady varieties (Open pollination), showed the highest seed yield weight of 5.33 g/Umbel and 4.33 g/Umbel, respectively, while the lowest seed yield was recorded from self-pollination with 0.36 g/Umbel from variety Baftaim, followed by Balady (0.22g/Umbel). On the other hand, the thousand-seed weight of Baftaim ranged from 3.16 to 4.44 g. The variety Baftaim with open pollination recorded the highest numbers (4.44 g), followed by the Balady variety (4.28 g) on the two types of pollination, while there is no significant difference between Balady and Baftaim statistically in self-pollination type. In the experimental farm site. Three groups of pollinators, viz., hymenopterans, lepidopterans, and dipterans, were recorded during the study. The total number of insect pollinators visited was 63.00. Among pollinators, hymenopterans were the main pollinating group, constituting 90.50%, followed by lepidopterans (6.33%) and dipterans (3.17%). The study proved the effectiveness of insect pollinators for onion seed production and recommended the importance of conserving those insect pollinators.

Introduction

Pollination is the process by which pollen is transferred to the female reproductive organs of a plant, thereby enabling fertilization to take place (Ollerton *et al.*, 2012). Hence, pollination is a keystone process in both human-managed and natural terrestrial ecosystems (Kearns and Inouye, 1993; Kevan, 1999; Donaldson, 2002; Richards and Kevan, 2002; de Jong *et al.*, 2005 and Collette, 2008). Over 80% of the crops grown in Europe are dependent on insect pollination (Potts *et al.*, 2010). Globally, up to 30% of the human food supply depends directly or indirectly on pollinators for fruit sets (McGregor, 1976, and Greenleaf and Kremen, 2006). The most likely reason for the unexpected yield declines detected in the past on insect-pollinated crops is a decline in insect pollinators (McGregor, 1976; Richards, 2001 and Ricketts, 2004). Up to 90% of all flowering plant species rely on pollination by insects such as bees (Buchmann and Nabhan, 1996). However, pollination value is often the most poorly understood and least likely to be optimized. In some cases, it is not managed at all, and growers just trust there will be enough bees or other insects in the vicinity of the crop to ensure that pollination occurs (Goodwin and Tustin, 2012).

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is ranked second after tomato in terms of total annual world production (Ambulker *et al.*, 1995, and Anon, 2007). It is a biennial crop for the purpose of seed production. In one season bulbs are produced from seeds, and in the second season bulbs are replanted to produce seeds. Inadequate pollination of the onion flower results in deformed and smaller seeds with low germination capacity (McGregor, 1976). This is because the onion flowers are not capable of self-pollinating, as the pollen

usually sheds before the female part in the flower is receptive (Protandry) (Lemma, 1998). So, the out-crossing becomes more critical due to the protandrous nature of the onion plant (Muller, 1983). So, the absence of natural pollinators on onion seed plantations poses a serious problem of reduction in seed number and seed weight per umbel. Also, seeds from free-pollination flowers show higher germination capacity than those isolated from insect visitors (Adel *et al.*, 2013).

Since onion produce good quality seed only in the presence of abundant pollinators and the quality of seed is directly proportional to the bulb yield in the successive generation (Chandel *et al.*, 2004) and among different pollinating agents, insects make a considerable contribution to the crop production, which is because 80% of the insect pollination of flowering plants, done by Bees (Gill *et al.*, 2012). Especially the honeybee, *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) (Nye *et al.*, 1973). Which is responding to the onion blooms that are characterized by rich pollen and high nectar content (Free, 1993, and Sajjad *et al.*, 2008).

Objectives

General objective

Efficacy of insect pollinators on seed production of two onion (*A. cepa* L.) varieties.

Specific objectives

- To evaluate the efficiency of insect pollinators on onion crops.
- To assess the seed yield of onion in tested varieties under insect pollinators.
- To identify the insect pollinators diversity associated with the onion crop.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental site:

The experiment was conducted in the experimental farm of the Faculty of

Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira, at Wad Medani, Latitude 14.44 North, Longitude 33.39 East and Altitude 407 meters above sea level, Gezira State, Sudan.

2. Plant material:

The onion bulbs of the two tested varieties, Baftaim and Balady, were collected from Wad Medani Central Market.

3. Onion pollination:

Onion pollination at the experimental farm is done by insect pollinators (Open pollination).

4. Land preparation and sowing:

Dry weeds and plant debris were cleaned, and the land was pre-watered. The grown weeds were removed by using Glyphosate at 1.1 liters per feddan. The land was plowed using a Disc plow. Clots were broken using a Disc Harrow. The Plant bed was prepared as a Mustabs of 1.00 m width and 5 meters length for each plot; the number of Mustabs was 3 per plot. Onion bulbs were sown at a 30 cm distance, and each hole contained one bulb, using manual labor. The experiment was irrigated on the same day. The experimental farm experiment was sown on Oct. 23, 2019. The experiment was arranged in a Completely Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with three replicates. Depending on condition, each experiment was irrigated every 7-10 days.

5. Experiment layout:

The experiments were composed of four different treatments in situ as follows:

T1 Variety Balady with open pollination.

T2 Variety Balady self-pollination.

T3 Variety Baftaim with open pollination.

T4 Variety Baftaim self-pollination.

6. Data collection:

Before the flowering of the crop, 10 inflorescence heads were selected randomly and covered with paper. This process was done in each plot. When about 10% of black seeds were visibly in the umbels, harvest was done. At harvesting time, the heads covered with paper sacs were collected, and a similar number from the same plots was harvested to test the efficacy of the insect pollinators compared to self-pollination plots. The data also included types of insects that were collected by swapping nets. The collected insects were pinned and labeled with date and site. Monitoring insect visitors for one hour between 8.00 and 9.00 in the morning. Insects were taken to the Agricultural Research Corporation (ARC) insect museum for identification. After maturity the collected heads were left to dry after each head was labeled and put into sac paper then subjected to 60°C in an oven for 24 hrs. Heads were weighed before and after threshing to draw the ratio of seeds in each umbel. To evaluate the efficacy of insect pollinators on the seed production of onion, different parameters like weight of seed yield per umbel, percentage of seed weight per umbel, and weight of 1000 seeds were measured with the help of an electronic balance. The data were collected for different parameters recorded from each cultivar under different treatments. Seeds weight ratio was measure with the help of formula given below:

$$\text{Seed weight ratio per head} = \frac{\text{Number of seed weight}}{\text{Number of head weight}} \times 100$$

7. Statistical analysis:

Analysis of variance was used to separate the means, and the degree of significance was achieved using the

Least Significant Difference Test (LSD) at P=0.05. For data analysis, use Statistic 8 software.

Results and discussion

Results of the present investigation of the effect of insect pollinators and pollination type on seed yield and various yield-attributing parameters of onion were studied under field conditions, as well as the insect pollinator diversity associated with the onion crop, which are presented below:

1. Effect of insect pollinators on onion seed yield:

The effect of type of pollination (Open pollination and self-pollination) on the seed production of two onion varieties at the experimental farm site was presented in Table (1). The results revealed a significant difference among treatments. Seed weight yield per umbel ranged from 5.33 to 0.36 g, open pollination type recorded high seed yield weight in the tested varieties (Baftaim 5.33 g and Balady 4.33 g), with the priority to the variety Baftaim. In the percentage of seed yield, the open pollination mode also recorded a high percentage range (56.00 for Balady to 58.67 for Baftaim) with no significant difference between them. Baftaim variety self-pollinated percentage (6.67%) and Balady self-pollinated (13%). On the other hand, the thousand-seed weight of Baftaim ranged from 3.16 to 4.44 g. The variety Baftaim with open pollination recorded the highest numbers (4.44 g), followed by the Balady variety (4.28 g) on the two types of pollination, while there is no significant difference between Balady and Baftaim statistically in self-pollination type. Data on onion seed yield production of two was presented in Table (2). The results revealed that statistically there were no significant differences between Baftaim and Balady varieties in seed yield product differences.

2. Diversity and abundance of the most frequent pollinators of the onion plants:

Pollinator fauna in onion-cultivated ecosystems of different pollinators that visited onion flowers are presented in Tables (3 and 4). The total number of pollinators visited was 63.00. Among these pollinators, hymenopterans were the main pollinating group, constituting 90.50%, followed by lepidopterans (6.33%) and dipterans (3.17%). Diversity and abundance of pollinators and insects are presented in Figure (1). The first week, the insects that visited the flower, a maximum population of *Megachile cyanipennis* Guérin-Méneville (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae) (10 insects/Umbel), were observed at 8:00-9:00 a.m., followed by *A. mellifera*, *Danaus chrysippus* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae) *Pieris mesentina* Moore and *Vespa carbro* (L.) (Hymenoptera: Vespidae) (Two insects/Umbel), *Chrysomya albiceps* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Calliphoridae) and *Xylocopa ustulata* Smith (Hymenoptera: Apidae) (One insect/Umbel). While, in the second week, the insects that visited the flower, maximum population of *M. cyanipennis* (Nine insects/Umbel) were observed, followed by *X. ustulata* (Six insects/Umbel), *A. mellifera* (Three workers/Umbel), *C. albiceps* (One insect/Umbel). On third week, the insects that visited the flower maximum population of *M. cyanipennis* (13 insects/Umbel) was observed, followed by *X. ustulata* Smith (Six insects/Umbel) and *A. mellifera* (Five workers/Umbel).

Generally, it was found that the most insects that visited the flower were *M. cyanipennis* (10.67 insects/Umbel) with an average of insect visits of three weeks, followed by *X. ustulata* (4.33 insects/ Umbel), *A. mellifera* (3.33 workers/ Umbel), *D. chrysippus*, *P. mesentina*, *V. carbro* and *C. albiceps* (0.67 insects / Umbel).

Table (1): Effect of pollination type on the seed production of the two onion varieties, Experimental Farm, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira, 2019-2020.

Treatment	*Seeds yield(g) /Umbel	*% of seed yield	*Thousand Seed Weight(g)
Baftaim (Open pollination)	5.33a	58.67a	4.44a
Baftaim (Self-pollination)	0.36c	6.67c	3.16b
Balady (Open pollination)	4.33b	56.00a	4.28a
Balady (Self-pollination)	0.22c	13.00b	3.21c
SE±	0.29	1.87	0.03
C.V %	14.02	6.51	1.06

*Mean of three replications. Means followed by some letter/s in columns are not significantly different according to LSD at $P \leq 0.05$.

Table (2): Onion seed yield production of two varieties, Gezira State, Sudan, 2019-2020.

Variety	Experimental site		
	Seeds yield (g)/Umbel	% of Seeds weight	Thousand Seed Weight(g)
Balady	2.83a	32.67a	3.74a
Baftaim	3.24a	34.50a	3.80a
SE±	0.43	2.06	0.05
C.V %	24.83	10.64	2.46

* Mean of three replications. Means followed by some letter/s in columns are not significantly different according to LSD at $P \leq 0.05$.

Table (3): A list of insect pollinators identified by the Agricultural Research Corporation (ARC) on onion crops in the experimental farm, 2019-2020–Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira, Gezira State, Sudan.

Scientific Name	Order	Family
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	Hymenoptera	Apidae
<i>Xylocopa ustulata</i>	Hymenoptera	Apidae
<i>Megachile cyanipennis</i>	Hymenoptera	Megachilidae
<i>Vespa carbro</i>	Hymenoptera	Vespidae
<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	Lepidoptera	Nymphalidae
<i>Pieris mesentina</i>	Lepidoptera	Pieridae
<i>Chrysomya albiceps</i>	Diptera	Calliphoridae
<i>Bruchus sp.</i>	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae
<i>Lygaeus sp.</i>	Hemiptera	Lygaeidae

Table (4): Some of the insect pollinators monitored on onion varieties at the experimental farm, 2019-2020–Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira.

Type of insect	Order	Number of insect visit			Means
		First week	Second week	Third week	
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	Hymenoptera	2	3	5	3.33
<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	Lepidoptera	2	0	0	0.67
<i>Pieris mesentina</i>	Lepidoptera	2	0	0	0.67
<i>Xylocopa ustulata</i>	Hymenoptera	1	6	6	4.33
<i>Megachile cyanipennis</i>	Hymenoptera	10	9	13	10.67
<i>Vespa carbro</i>	Hymenoptera	2	0	0	0.67
<i>Chrysomya albiceps</i>	Diptera	1	1	0	0.67
Total		20	19	24	21.01
Means		2.86	2.71	3.43	3

* Some insect pollinators were monitored on the onion crop for a period of three weeks for one hour per week, from 8.00 to 9.00 in the morning.

Figure (1): Some insect pollinators were monitored on the onion crop for a period of three weeks for one hour per week, from 8.00 to 9.00 in the morning at the experimental farm site.

A range of studies showed that pollinators made a very significant contribution to the agricultural production of different crops, particularly fruits, vegetables, fiber crops, and nuts (Levin, 1984; Costanza *et al.*, 1997; and Gordon and Davis, 2003). Onion plants are often visited by insects, and among these, honeybees are most effective (Saeed *et al.*, 2008; Sajjad *et al.*, 2008; Walker *et al.*, 2011; and Brand, 2014). Worldwide, many agricultural crops are pollinated either totally or partially by bees. Of the known pollinator species, honeybees (*A. mellifera*) are the most important due to their abundance and manageability by beekeepers. Other species of bees such as bumble bees and leaf-cutter bees provide pollination services in some areas, but their population numbers are variable and difficult to manage (Walsh, 1965).

The results obtained in this study indicated a significant increase in the weight of seed yield per umbel, weight of a thousand seeds, and percentage of seed weight per umbel in the plants' open pollination compared with self-pollination. This could be attributed to the effect of insects as efficient

pollinators of the onion plant. These results are partially in agreement with the findings of Devi *et al.* (2026), who found the average seed weight of onion was maximum (22.96g/5 Umbels) under open pollination which was significantly higher than the seed weight under self-pollination (2.23g/5 Umbels). Woyke (1981) observed that the numbers and weight of onion seeds from self-pollination, were very low as compared with yields on open fields provided by honeybee colonies. Yucel and Duman (2005) reported that the seed yield per bulb was higher in open plots (5.74 g/Umbel) than in caged plots (1.29 g/Umbel). Total seed yield per plot was 898.95 g/plot on the open side. Whereas it was 220.65 g/plot in caged groups. Kandakoor and Hilli (2020) observed that the maximum number of seeds per umbel was observed in open-pollinated flowers with 339.30 ± 60.27 seeds per umbel, where all four species of bees made visits regularly, followed by the case of pollination in a mesh cloth cage with bees with 330.00 ± 35.80 , and the very least number of seed sets was observed in the case of pollination in a mesh cloth cage without bees with only 60.70 seeds/Umbel.

Munawar *et al.* (2011) found that onion seed setting is dependent on insect pollination. Walker *et al.* (2011) found that self-pollination umbels set significantly fewer seeds (Average 8 seeds/Umbel, n=10) than hand-pollinated umbels (Average 146 seeds/umbel) and free pollination umbels (Average 481 seeds/Umbel). Sajjad *et al.* (2008) found that caged plants produced (130 seeds/Umbel) whereas open-pollinated plants produced 932 seeds/Umbel). Rao and Lazar (1983) observed only 9.8% seed setting in onion in cages. Moreover, Kumar *et al.* (1989) recorded three times more yield in open-pollinated treatment than the closed one. Also, Saurabh and Mandal (2018) found the number of seeds produced per umbel was much higher in open-pollinated fields (851.29) as compared to those without pollinators (18.72). However, owing to the low attractiveness of onion flowers, pollination is often inadequate, resulting in low seed yields (Soto *et al.*, 2013).

Furthermore, this result was similar to Saurabh and Mandal (2018), who found the open pollination significantly increased the 1000-seed weight of the onion (3.65 g) as compared to it without any pollinator (2.67 g). Kandakoor and Hilli (2020) observed that 1000 seed weight also differed significantly in the case of pollination with and without bees. In case of bees, it weighed around 3.37 g/1000 seeds followed by 3.10 g/1000 seeds in onion with bee cage and least in case of control with only 1.97 g/1000 seeds. Similarly, Ahmad *et al.* (2003) found that reduced or limited visiting of pollinators caused a 50-61% reduction in onion seed production.

In another study, Ahmad *et al.* (2003) found no significant difference in attraction of pollinators to the four varieties of onion. However, varieties possessing a higher concentration of nectar in flowers are more attractive to

insect pollinators, which in turn could result in a better seed setting.

It was noticed in this experiment that the production covered without insects was very weak. These partials agree with McGregor (1976), who also found that self-seed sprouts more slowly and production is lower than plants derived from crossed seed. In the present study higher values of no significant difference were reported in the open pollination than in the self-pollinated system regarding all the parameters studied.

The results of insect pollinators of the experimental farm are similar to the findings of Sajjad *et al.* (2008), who found the onion umbels are visited by honeybees, small syrphid flies, bumblebees, halictid bees, drone flies, butterflies, and insects of minor importance with respect to pollination. Also, Bohart *et al.* (1970) reported 267 species of insect visitors on onion flowers, the most important of which were honeybees, small syrphid flies, halictid bees, and drone flies. Of these, only the honeybee can be manipulated and used in large-scale onion seed production. Chandel *et al.* (2004) stated that in various regions of India, the most effective onion pollinators were *A. dorsata* Fab., followed by *A. cerana* Fab., *A. florea* Fab. (Hymenoptera: Apidae), and *A. mellifera*. Also, the Syrphidae family, order Diptera, takes part in the process of pollination. Kordakova (1956) and Sakharov (1956) gave major credit to the honeybee as a pollinator of onions in Russia.

Also, our results found insect visitors on onion umbels are visited by honeybees (*A. mellifera*), *D. chrysippus*, *P. mesentina*, *X. ustulata* Smith, *M. cyanipennis*, *V. carbro*, *C. albiceps*, and insects of minor importance with respect to onion pollination. Similarly, McGregor (1976) and Free (1993) reported that insects like ants, aphids, bees, beetles,

butterflies, flies, midges, mosquitoes, moths, thrips, and wasps act as pollinators in cultivated crops. Among them, bees are considered the most important pollinators because they are the only insects whose immature stages are reared exclusively on pollen and nectar (Crane, 1990).

Insect pollinator species are the primary pollinating agents for onions, and they are the most effective in increasing crop yield and quality. Insect pollinators of flowers visits onion fields to obtain increased onion seed yield, better quality, and more quantity of onion seeds to ensure the availability of quality onion seeds for commercial bulb production. There were 9 insect pollinator species identified in the location of the study. Identified insect pollinator species belong to Hymenoptera (4 species), Lepidoptera (2 species), Hemiptera (1 species), Diptera (1 species), and Coleoptera (1 species), ordered. The Baftaim variety recorded the highest seed yield mean of (3.80 g), while Balady recorded the highest 1000-seed weight mean of (3.74 g).

The study recommended that pollination is an essential input in the production of the onion crop, and this crop requires pollination for improving quality as well as enhancing yield. Also, insect pollinators visit onion flowers to increase seed production.

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